

EVALUATION OF IMMUNOLOGICAL INDICATORS IN PATIENTS WITH RHINOSINUSITIS.

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Abstract: This study was conducted to investigate the effects of interleukins in rhinosinusitis.

Relevance: In the last decade, an increase in the frequency of allergic respiratory diseases has been observed all over the world. According to the etiological factor, allergic rhinitis is divided into seasonal and permanent/household. Persistent allergic rhinitis is one of the most common allergic diseases, the number of which is increasing every year.

The purpose of the research: determination and comparison of immunological indicators in patients with persistent allergic rhinitis and catarrhal rhinosinusitis.

Research materials and methods. The study was conducted at the base of the Tashkent Medical Academy clinic and the Republican Allergology Center. Two main groups of 60 patients with permanent allergic rhinitis and 30 patients with catarrhal rhinosinusitis were selected for examination. During the examination, clinical, microbiological and laboratory analyzes were performed on both groups of patients. All patients underwent immunological examination, i.e. serum IgE level and IL-4, IL-13 concentration.

Results. According to our results, the amount of IgE detected in mine serum was more than 3 times higher in RS patients with persistent allergic rhinitis than in patients with catarrhal rhinosinusitis (105.8ME/ml and 316.0ME/ml, respectively). Our indicators revealed that the amount of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-4 and IL-13 increased reliably in our group I patients compared to group II patients with catarrhal rhinosinusitis. 16.14 in our group I patients; 7.64 pg/ml; In our group II patients, it was 7.87 and 3.28 pg/ml.

Summary. As a result of the study of cytokines IL4 and IL13, we observed a reliable increase in the indicators in patients with persistent allergic rhinitis compared to patients with catarrhal rhinosinusitis. Identifying these indicators in the early stages and creating a treatment plan will help prevent complications and improve the patient's quality of life.

Keywords: Rhinosinusitis, allergic rhinitis, interleukin, cytokines

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